

EU FAR Project

Research results useful for evidence-based policy making

Newsletter April, 2023

Project Insights

EU FAR offers publicly available data on EU funding for all Romanian municipalities, for the entire programming period of 2014-2020. The work stimulates development of granular open data on EU funding and provides evidence-based analyses for fostering balanced territorial development. The methodology for computing aggregated sums can be further replicated across other EU countries for fostering comparable large research datasets. The project deliverables are disseminated with the support of services included in the European Open Science Cloud catalogue.

Methodology

Description of data aggregation and list of variables in EU FAR v1 database.

Dataset

Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality from Romania at LAU 2 level.

Other materials

Explore leaflets, animation, presentations, and other information.

This project has received funding from the European Union' Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. [101017536](#).

Project deliverables

Key words
EU funds, localities, open science, Romania

Organization
Research Institute for Quality of Life (RIQL), Romanian Academy, Bucharest

Project team
Project Coordinator: Monica Marin
Technical Experts: Eugen Glăvan, Alin Chiș and Bogdan Corad

Timeframe
October 2022 – March 2023

Webpage
<https://www.iccv.ro/en/projects/eu-far-eu-funds-by-area-results-en/>

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It is supported by the Research Data Alliance through the RDA Open Calls as part of the EO SC Future project.

European Funds
by area results

The key objective of the EU FAR project is to stimulate development of granular open data on EU funding. In doing so, the work will be conducted for Romania by providing open data aligned with the FAIR movement (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability). Information publicly displayed by the project is focused on the EU funds absorbed by local governments in Romania (LAU 2 level). The project will cover available data for the entire programming period of 2014-2020.

The activities involve a mix of policy analysis and dissemination work targeting relevant stakeholders at various levels: local, county, regional, national and EU levels. A special focus will be placed on rural areas. Deliverables include open database, policy briefs, conference paper, presentations and an open-access academic article. The processing and public display of data will make use of Research Data Alliance (RDA) outputs. The project's deliverables will be disseminated with the support of the European Open Science Cloud (EO SC) services and products. The project team envisages a sustainability plan to ensure further uptake of project's outputs at a larger scale.

Latest Informations

Maps based on EU Funds Absorbed by Romanian Municipalities database

EU FAR - Addressing territorial disparities in EU funds absorption

Policy Brief

Addressing territorial disparities in EU funds absorption. Policy brief

The maps are graphical representations of the volume of EU funds by municipality and by county.

Key findings and policy implication: EU FAR Project tackles the issue of place-based EU funding.

Online Workshop: presentation about EU FAR Project results

The workshop for presenting and discussing the results of the EU FAR project was organized online by RIQL, Romanian Academy, on February 28th, 2023. Additional presentations have been delivered by representatives of [RDA Node RO](#) and the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#) about EOSC and EOSC Future, the Romanian Association of Communes, and the Romanian Association of Towns.

RDA/EOSC Future Project Grantee Spotlight: Monica Marin

The Research Data Alliance website hosts an interview with Monica Marin, the EU FAR project coordinator, about work and experiences within the project and future plans.

[Read more...](#)

EU FAR Database in CESSDA

The EU FAR Database: EU Funds Absorbed by Romanian Municipalities 2016–2021 is registered within the Czech Social Science Data Archive and will be listed in the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives catalogue.

[View database...](#)

EU FAR Perspectives

"Unless you have granular data on EU funds absorbed by each municipality, you can not objectively assess the accomplishment of objectives related to reducing territorial disparities. Rural areas in particular face multiple disadvantages and a careful look taken at them is precisely what the analysis does."

Anca Monica Marin

[Read more...](#)

Future Actions

The project will soon end administratively, but we will continue the work to provide a complete image of EU funding in Romania for the entire past programming period for all municipalities. The project's team will update the EU FAR database with information from 2022 and 2023 once it becomes available. In addition, it will use census population data (Census 2021, conducted in 2022) to yield more accurate estimations on funds per capita.

We will keep you informed on the database updates, as well as on any additional developments.

Useful Links

[Horizon Europe - Research and innovation - European Union](#)

[RDA | Research Data Sharing without barriers](#)

[Research Institute for Quality of Life, Romanian Academy](#)

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